

1 From groups to communities in western lowland

2 gorillas

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23 Social networks are the result of interactions between individuals at different temporal scales. Thus,
24 sporadic intergroup encounters and individual forays play a central role in defining the dynamics of
25 populations in social species. We assessed the rate of intergroup encounters for three western lowland
26 gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla gorilla*) groups with daily observations over five years, and noninvasively
27 genotyped a larger population over four months. Both approaches revealed a social system much
28 more dynamic than anticipated, with nonaggressive intergroup encounters that involved social play by
29 immature individuals, exchanges of members between groups likely modulated by kinship, and
30 absence of infanticide evidenced by infants non fathered by the silverback of the group where they
31 were found. This resulted in a community composed of groups that interacted frequently and non-
32 aggressively, contrasting with the more fragmented and aggressive mountain gorilla (*G. beringei*
33 *beringei*) societies. Such extended sociality can promote the sharing of behavioural and cultural traits,
34 but might also increase the susceptibility of western lowland gorillas to infectious diseases that have
35 decimated their populations in recent times.

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39 **Keywords**

40 *Gorilla*, sociality, community, kinship, infanticide, infectious diseases.

41 **1. Introduction**

42 Understanding the processes driving the structure of animal societies is a non-trivial exercise
43 which requires disentangling stable social networks from dynamic spatio-temporal patterns [1]. In
44 this context, temporal demographic changes and dispersal are the major drivers of variability in
45 social group size, but are complemented with short-term segregation/aggregation events and
46 intergroup interactions [2]. These lead to social structures above the group level with varying levels
47 of complexity and dynamism. Social structure and behaviour are adaptive response to
48 environmental pressures, and flexibility in social organisation may facilitate reactions to varying
49 environmental conditions [3]. Information on social structure is highly relevant in wildlife ecology,
50 conservation and management [4]. However, highly dynamic social structures can make the
51 interpretation of social processes and their evolutionary significance a challenging task [2]

52 Western lowland gorillas (WLG; *Gorilla gorilla gorilla*) offer the possibility of studying the
53 potentially complex social structure in a great ape in areas with minimal human impact. The global
54 population of this primate, recently estimated at about 360,000 individuals [5], has suffered a
55 dramatic decline mainly due to massive die-offs caused by *Ebolavirus* outbreaks, and the
56 forecasts predict further sharp declines [6]. This great ape from the lowland forests and swamps of
57 western central Africa (see figure S1 in supplementary material) lives in groups generally
58 consisting of one fully mature male (silverback) and several adult females with their offspring, or in
59 non-breeding groups [7-9].

60 Compared to the better-studied mountain gorilla (*G. beringei beringei*), the structure and
61 dynamics of social groups in WLG are poorly understood [10,11]. This bias is due to the higher
62 mobility and lower observability of WLG, impairing simultaneous monitoring of multiple groups [12].
63 For this reason, most of the information of social interactions in WLG have been gathered in *bais*,
64 which are easily monitored but rare swampy clearings in the forest where groups commingle while
65 feeding on grasses rich in salts [13] and are [7-9,14,15]. These observations suggest that one of
66 the most striking differences between the two gorilla species is in their social behaviour. While

67 mountain gorilla group interactions are frequently aggressive, WLG groups interact non-
68 aggressively [10]. Concordantly, infanticide is frequently observed in mountain gorillas, while it has
69 never been reported in WLG [9,16]. Also, group takeovers by outside males do not occur in WLG
70 [9,16,17] as opposed to mountain gorillas [18]. WLG groups have just one silverback, in contrast
71 with the frequent multi-silverback groups of mountain gorillas, where more than 15% of the infants
72 are not sired by the dominant male [19]. Nevertheless, *bais* are sites where gorillas spend just 1%
73 of their time [20] and not all groups have access to them. Thus, social interactions there might not
74 be representative of what happens hidden in the dense inaccessible forests, where resources may
75 be more limiting. In this context, assessing the degree and extent of association between social
76 groups at a small spatial scale and over a short time period is key to understand spatial
77 organisation and resource use. This knowledge is needed to implement effective predictive models
78 of infectious disease transmission at large spatial and temporal scales, to interpret evolutionary
79 processes, and to develop suitable conservation and management strategies. This is particularly
80 important because 77% of the WLG range falls outside protected areas, making this great ape
81 particularly vulnerable to logging and poaching [5].

82 In order to shed light on the social dynamics of the western lowland gorilla, we explored
83 intergroup interactions of three breeding groups that were habituated to the presence of observers
84 and were monitored daily in Ngaga Forest, located in one of the last stronghold for this great ape.
85 Here, a dense population that has not been affected by Ebola outbreaks in the last decades still
86 thrive. Additionally, we conducted an intensive noninvasive genetic survey over a larger area to
87 identify neighbouring groups and solitary individuals and to investigate their relatedness. This
88 intense monitoring allowed us to assess if interactions between members of different social units
89 (breeding and non-breeding groups, as well as solitary individuals) were frequent, and to
90 investigate the role of kinship on these interactions. The results revealed a surprisingly dynamic
91 western lowland gorilla society, characterised by frequent non-aggressive intergroup interactions
92 likely facilitated by very low rates of infanticide.

93 **2. Methods**

94 **(a) Monitoring of focal groups**

95 We monitored three focal groups (FG1, FG2 and FG3) of habituated western lowland gorilla in
96 Ngaga Forest, on the southwestern boundary of Odzala-Kokoua National Park (Republic of the
97 Congo, 0°40'N-14°60'E, figure S1) from 2013 to 2017 (about 305 monitoring sessions per group
98 and year). The home ranges of these groups overlap and the identity of each member was well
99 known. Expert trackers and researchers located the animals early in the morning, normally before
100 they left the nesting site and noted their behaviour between 07.00 and 16.00 h for an average of 2
101 h/day per focal group (range: 1 to 5 h). Although the groups were successfully located on most
102 days, detailed observations were often limited by the dense vegetation. Behavioural data were
103 recorded by M.B. and G.I. using instantaneous scan sampling, focal individual sampling, and
104 observations *ad libitum* [21]. We conducted instantaneous scan samples at 5-min intervals, to
105 measure the amount of time that each individual was in view, the amount of time spent feeding on
106 fruit, feeding on other food resources, resting, involved in social interactions, or travelling. During
107 times of intergroup encounters, we stopped all other data collection and started collecting data on
108 the intergroup interactions. We used all-occurrence sampling of behaviours focusing on aggressive
109 (such as fighting, chasing, fleeing, spatial avoidance, biting, beating, and displacement) and
110 affiliative behaviours (such as embraces, touch, grooming, play, sit in contact and social mount)
111 [22]. We watched multiple individuals and recorded behaviours at one-minute intervals. We
112 compiled information about encounters between the focal groups (summarised in figure S2) or
113 between them and other groups. Some examples of these interactions are described in table S1.
114 Only the encounters in which we could individually identify with certainty the participants from both
115 groups were included in this study. Throughout the duration of our study the focal groups varied in
116 size (FG1: 15 to 17 individuals; FG2: 15 to 24 individuals; FG3: 22 to 26 individuals) as a
117 consequence of birth, death and dispersal events, yet always remaining under the leadership of
118 the same silverback male.

119 The accompanying video S1 (<https://www.flickr.com/gp/revillaeloy/T55d36>) shows four half-
120 minute recordings of an encounter (an event during which members of different social units
121 maintain visual contact with one another in close proximity, usually less than 10 m) between two
122 non-focal groups obtained using camera traps to exemplify some of the observed interactions (two-
123 way actions between members of different social units). The interactions were considered
124 aggressive when consisting of or escalating into any physical harassment or threatening
125 behaviour. The specific encounter filmed in the video lasted for 279 minutes during which
126 individuals of the two groups fed and interacted non-aggressively. In particular, the video shows
127 juveniles of the two groups playing together, occasionally under close monitoring by older
128 individuals that tolerated their interactions. It also shows that social play could be gentle or rough.
129 Gentle play included behaviours such as tickling, jumping, and gentle wrestling. Rough play
130 included more rigorous and acrobatic behaviours such as play fighting, twirling, chasing, and
131 pushing, which were often punctuated by transitional periods of low activity. In general, play
132 sessions started when an individual first directed a playful pattern towards another and ended
133 when the playmates stopped their activities or one of them moved away. Within social play, we
134 distinguished between locomotor-rotational play (including play recovering an item, play run,
135 pirouetting, sliding down) when a session was characterised by the absence of any kind of physical
136 contact between the playmates, and play fighting (including biting, pushing, pulling, slapping,
137 stamping, retrieving, brusque rushing), when the participants exhibited physical contact.
138 Nevertheless, play sessions can sometimes escalate into overt aggressions when ending with
139 screaming and/or bared teeth by one of the players as well as with an aggressive interaction (e.g.,
140 chase/flee) [22].

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143 **(b) Noninvasive sample collection**

144 A total of 279 faecal samples were collected in Ngaga Forest between May and August 2013

145 (Dataset S1). The sampling area stretched over ca. 44 km² mostly covered by dense forest with
146 closed canopy and abundant Marantaceae understory. No *bais* are present in Ngaga forest. Fresh
147 gorilla traces were searched along trails by expert local trackers and traced back to locate night
148 nests.

149 Faeces were collected from the nests and we assumed that dungs associated with different
150 nests at a given nesting site were likely to correspond to different individual members of the same
151 group. Overall, we sampled 21-25 putative groups that were identified as distinct based on
152 distance between nesting sites (>1 km) and number of nests per site (possibly informative
153 regarding group size). Opportunistic sampling was also carried out along trails when track
154 evidence suggested the presence of just one individual (solitary individuals are difficult to track and
155 therefore their nests cannot be easily found). The sampled groups included only two (FG1 and
156 FG2) out of the three focal groups subject to daily monitoring while the third one (FG3) could not
157 be located with certainty within the study area at the time of faecal sampling. However, we cannot
158 rule out that one of the non-focal groups sampled in the periphery of the study area corresponded
159 to FG3.

160 Age class for each sample was estimated from bolus diameter for the majority of the faeces
161 [23]. However, such categorization in the field is prone to errors. Age class was ultimately
162 confirmed for the individuals whose genealogy could be established in relatedness analyses (see
163 below). Silverback samples were identified based on the comparatively bigger size of nest and
164 dung, as well as on the occurrence of whitish hairs in the nest. Latitude and longitude coordinates
165 were recorded for each sample or nesting site using a handheld GPS. Approximately 5-10 g of
166 each faeces was placed in tubes with silica beads and later stored at -80° C in the laboratory. All
167 research was carried out with permission from the *Agence Nationale des Parcs Nationaux* and the
168 *Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique et Technique* of the Republic of the Congo.

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171 **(c) DNA isolation and amplification**

172 DNA isolation was performed from about 10 mg of faeces following the
173 hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) protocol as modified by Vallet *et al* [24]. Extracts
174 were eluted in TE buffer (Tris 10mM, EDTA 1mM, pH 8.5) and stored at -20°C. Subsequent
175 amplifications were performed in physically isolated laboratory facilities with negative controls
176 being routinely included at each step of the laboratory workflow to check for possible
177 contamination. Sex was assessed by targeting a fragment of the X-Y amelogenin homologous
178 gene as in Bradley *et al.* [25] and the SRY gene as in Di Fiore [26]. Samples were genotyped at 17
179 tetranucleotide autosomal microsatellite loci using fluorescently labelled primers and multiplex
180 amplifications as in Le Gouar *et al.* [27]. Separation of PCR products was achieved by capillary
181 electrophoresis on an ABI 3130XL sequencer (Applied Biosystems) with an internal size standard
182 (GENESCAN-500 LIZ). Each locus was amplified between two and twelve times for each faecal
183 sample. Consensus individual multilocus genotypes were obtained by comparing genotypes
184 retrieved in independent reactions. While heterozygous genotypes were confirmed with at least two
185 independent replicates, homozygous needed three to four replicates depending on the locus
186 variability. This number of replicates was adjusted considering allelic dropout and false allele rates
187 estimated by comparing consensus genotypes to PCR replicates [28]. This approach allows a by-
188 locus genotyping scheme by minimising mistyping due to false alleles and allelic dropout rates.
189 Only individual faeces successfully genotyped at a minimum of six loci were retained for further
190 analyses. This threshold enabled a reliable individual identification ($P(ID)_{sib} < 0.01$, see below).

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193 **(d) Individual identification and genetic variability**

194 Identification of faeces deposited by the same individual was carried out with GENECAP [29] and
195 CERVUS v.3.0.7 [30]. These programs identify exact matches and estimate the probability of
196 identity among siblings, $P(ID)_{sib}$, a more conservative estimation of the probability that two random

197 individuals from the population share the same genotype, $P(ID)$, by considering the presence of
198 close relatives. Two or more samples were considered as recaptures of the same individual when
199 their multilocus genotypes were identical at all loci typed in both samples (≥ 6 loci; this minimum
200 number of identical loci was chosen to obtain $P(ID)sib$ values within the range recommended for
201 noninvasive studies: $0.0001 < P(ID)sib < 0.01$ [31]). Since faecal samples are prone to genotyping
202 errors due to false alleles and allelic dropout, they could result in slightly different genotypes for the
203 same individual. We first used MM-DIST [32] to obtain distributions of pairwise mismatches for the
204 empirical data and for pairs of simulated genotypes with different degrees of kinship (parent-
205 offspring, full-siblings and unrelated individuals). The empirical frequencies for mismatches at one
206 or two loci were 0.004 and 0.01, respectively, yet simulated values were always orders of
207 magnitude lower (< 0.0001) for all kinship categories. This strongly suggested that genotyping
208 errors could be responsible for most of the cases of mismatches at just one or two loci. The R
209 package allelematch [33] confirmed two as the maximum number of mismatching alleles tolerated
210 as possible genotyping errors. Consequently, genotypes differing by one or two alleles were
211 considered recaptures of the same individual.

212 Samples from the same individual and collected on the same date and location were
213 considered the same capture event and not recaptures (for example, multiple faecal samples from
214 the same individual in a group of nests, collected assuming that they could correspond to different
215 individuals, $n=52$). A total of 86 faeces represented recaptures which were collected up to nine
216 different dates. Once we established the final set of unique individual genotypes, population allele
217 frequencies were calculated using GENALEX v.6.502 [34,35]. Expected (H_E) and observed (H_O)
218 heterozygosity were computed with ARLEQUIN v.3.5.2.2 [36]. The number of alleles per locus
219 ranged from six to 18, and average (\pm SD) H_E and H_O were 0.759 (± 0.097) and 0.760 (± 0.088),
220 respectively.

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223 **(e) Social unit identification, structure and transfer of individuals between groups**

224 We used a hierarchical version of the network community detection algorithm Infomap [37]
225 (<http://www.mapequation.org/code.html>) to identify sets of genotypes (individuals) that tended to
226 occur together across time and space. Co-occurrence was taken as evidence of membership in the
227 same social unit and allowed inferring the number of social groups sampled in the genetic survey.
228 We adopted this method because it is known to outperform similar approaches in terms of
229 recovering the optimal network topology [38]. Specifically, the social structure of our sample was
230 explored by drawing a modular social network associated with a co-occurrence matrix connecting
231 each individual to the others based on the instances when they were sampled together in the same
232 day and in the same nesting site. We ran Infomap by using the individuals (identified by the
233 genotypes) as nodes and the co-occurrence patterns as links. In other words, we created a link
234 between two individuals that slept in the same nesting site. We carried out 10,000 runs and chose
235 the best network on the basis of the code length indicator [37].

236 This approach also allowed the identification of individuals that were associated to different
237 groups on different dates, implying transfers between these groups. These transfers were
238 responsible for the hierarchical modular structure found in the population. Due to the difficulties
239 associated with genotype reconstruction from faeces (see above), we paid close attention to the
240 genotypes of these individuals to make sure that none of them was associated with potential
241 genotyping errors.

242 We estimated relatedness (r) between individual genotypes with COANCESTRY [39]. Since
243 identical relatedness values are expected for full siblings and for parent-offspring pairs, dyadic
244 relatedness values were complemented with genealogy reconstruction to differentiate the two
245 possibilities using COLONY [40] (see Supplementary Methods).

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249 **(f) Distribution of relatedness values in the population**

250 The distribution of pairwise relatedness estimates between and within sexes as well as between
251 and within social units and across space was explored by permutation analyses (10,000
252 permutations) implemented in *ad hoc* Microsoft Excel macros developed by Lukas *et al.* [41] (see
253 Supplementary Methods).

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256 **3. Results**

257 **(a) Monitoring of focal groups**

258 During the five years of intense monitoring we observed gorilla focal groups on 1525 days. We
259 registered a minimum of 34 daytime intergroup encounters involving exclusively the focal groups
260 (lasting 30 h in total) and of which four were encounters of all three groups. In addition we
261 observed three encounters with non-focal groups, although the real number could be higher
262 because these groups avoid being close to humans. Overall, the rate of intergroup encounter was
263 2% (34 in 1525 monitoring days) for the three focal groups. Because of the limited visibility in the
264 dense Marantaceae understory, the observed encounters represented a gross underestimate of
265 the total encounter rate. During these events 39 to 55 gorillas would meet with distances of less
266 than 10 m between groups and even with direct contact between members of the different groups.
267 We found that the frequency of encounters between pairs of groups was quite heterogeneous and
268 some groups met more often than others (figure S2). All interactions among members of different
269 groups were non-aggressive, lasting from a few minutes to several hours, and included feeding on
270 the same resources and social play, typically between immature individuals. In addition, we also
271 observed social play between adults; adult females played with each other as well as with
272 immature individuals, suggesting a high motivation to engage in such interactions (see video S1).
273 Interestingly, silverbacks were very tolerant towards these activities, closely monitoring the
274 individuals involved in the interactions and staying a few meters apart, but without showing any

275 aggressive behaviour. Social play involving members of two or three groups required a high degree
276 of reciprocity, cooperation and communication between play mates (for some examples of
277 interactions see table S1).

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280 **(b) Noninvasive genotyping**

281 We collected a total of 279 gorilla faecal samples (Dataset S1). Molecular sexing was successful
282 for 277 of these and failed for the other two due to low quality DNA. Overall, 144 male and 133
283 female faeces were found. Of these, 254 samples were scored at a minimum of six loci and
284 retained in downstream analyses. Among these we identified 125 different individuals and on
285 average their genotypes (Dataset S2) were complete for 94% of the loci. Of these individuals, 64
286 (51%) were males and 61 (49%) females. Allelic dropout and false allele error rates per locus
287 ranged from 0.01 to 0.15 and 0.02 to 0.10, respectively. The $P(ID)sib$ per locus ranged from 0.300
288 to 0.508, and reached 1.32×10^{-7} for the entire set of loci.

289 We used the information of the genotype profiles and their collection site and date to infer
290 putative groups. Some of the groups were located multiple times (figure 1a). Field (presence of
291 white hairs in nests or faeces) and genetic (confirmed paternities) suggested the presence of 14
292 candidate silverbacks, 9 of which were found within putative groups (one per group). The
293 remaining 5 plus 4 other individuals (two males and two females) were always sampled alone (on
294 up to two different occasions: figure 1a).

295 Interestingly, 6 individuals appeared integrated within different putative groups at different
296 times, complicating the definition of social units. Hence, we used a network community algorithm to
297 identify social groups based on the frequency at which individuals were sampled together. This
298 analysis yielded a modular structure [2], with multiple social groups and some individuals sampled
299 alone. We identified 16 groups composed of 2 to 17 individuals (figure 1b). We found nine breeding
300 groups (FG1, FG2, G3, G7, G8, G9, G10, G12 and G15) defined by parent-offspring relationships

301 between group members, one bachelor group (a social unit mostly including immature individuals,
302 male-biased and with no reproductively active females [7]: G13, composed of at least 10 males
303 and one immature female), and six more non-breeding groups (G4, G5, G6, G11, G14 and G16:
304 figure 1c) including adult individuals of both sexes but no offspring.

305 One of the groups, G9, was resampled on five occasions in different locations, but the
306 group composition was never the same (figure 1a). The resampling data showed a clear internal
307 structure in the pattern of co-occurrence (figure 2). The silverback was repeatedly sampled with
308 one immature male (one of his sons) and two adult females, whereas other adult females and
309 immature members of the group were found with them less often. The fact that immature animals
310 were resampled less often within the rest of the group suggests that they frequently spent the night
311 separated from the group. The same pattern was found for all groups that were sampled on
312 multiple occasions: the resampling probability was lower for immature individuals than for adults
313 (0.68 vs 0.88, $Z=-2.679$, $P<0.007$; 95%CI: 0.57-0.77 vs 0.79-0.94).

314 Our results indicate hierarchical modularity in the population structure, with several groups
315 assembling into larger entities due to their dynamic composition. Despite the short sampling
316 period, five groups (G3, G6, G7, G8, G16) joined into a “supergroup” connected by some
317 individuals that were sampled in different groups at different times (figures 1a and 1b). Two males
318 moved from social groups composed mostly of unrelated individuals to their natal groups (from G8
319 and G16 to G7 and G3, respectively; figure 1c, table S4). On the other hand, two females moved
320 between groups (from G7 to G6 and G8 to G16) with silverbacks that were unrelated to them in
321 both groups and, thus, were not their natal groups in either case. In addition, two females from
322 group FG1 joined a roaming male maybe in an attempt to establish a separate reproductive group,
323 G5 (figures 1a and 1b). The remaining groups appeared as distinct social units (figure 1b), but the
324 fact that some were observed only once impaired the identification of additional intergroup
325 transfers. In addition, a group-living female was later resampled alone, and two individuals (one
326 female and one male) were first found alone and later integrated into groups.

327 The distribution of pairwise genetic relatedness r , after excluding the offspring in parent-
328 offspring pairs within social units (to exclude pre-dispersal individuals), was very similar for adult
329 females and males, with similarly skewed distributions indicating that the majority of individuals
330 were unrelated ($0 < r < 0.1$; figure S3). Neither Mantel tests ($R=0.003$; $P > 0.05$; figure S4) nor
331 permutation tests based on different distance categories ($P > 0.05$) revealed association between
332 geographic distance and genetic relatedness in adult males or females. Nevertheless, permutation
333 tests revealed that adult females ($n=45$) within the same group tended to be more related than
334 expected ($P=0.01$) indicating that related females had settled in the same group after dispersal.
335 However, relatedness between females and silverbacks in their own group was as expected by
336 chance alone ($n=35$, $P=0.42$).

337 To assess the origin of males found alone, we compared them to silverbacks. Resident group-
338 leading silverbacks ($n=9$) were not more related to each other than to lone adult males ($n=8$,
339 $P=0.37$). The males always found alone (presumably solitary individuals) were excluded as
340 offspring of resident silverbacks. However, three of them had offspring in the bachelor group (G13)
341 and in non-breeding groups (G6, G16; figure 1c).

342 Pedigree reconstruction confirmed that the father of pre-dispersal individuals (immatures
343 with their parents in the same group) usually was the resident silverback (in 38 out of 41 cases,
344 93%; figure 1c). The only exceptions were three females (in groups G3 and G9) whose father
345 could not be identified in our sample. On the other hand, mothers could be identified in the group
346 for only 61% (23 out of 38) of the offspring sired by the silverbacks. In two cases the mothers were
347 identified in another group within the study area (both immature individuals in group G12, with their
348 mothers in group G11). In one more instance neither the father nor the mother could be identified
349 within the group (G12).

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353 **4. Discussion**

354 Our results unveil a social system much more dynamic than anticipated in WLG with entire
355 groups meeting and interacting, frequent exchanges of individuals between groups, and groups
356 that varied in composition over a period of a few days implying limited cohesiveness.

357 Other studies have considered WLG group dynamics in the longer term, showing social
358 units that appear, split or disappear [42-44]. However, group dynamics here do not merely result
359 from individual birth, death or migration, but reflect an ever-changing society over a short time.
360 Temporary associations to different social units in some cases involved individuals moving to
361 groups hosting relatives. Nevertheless, this dynamic social structure went beyond family groups
362 and the possible benefits of inclusive fitness. Some males were observed to return to their natal
363 group; the fact that they had temporarily been in a group with unrelated individuals entails transient
364 acceptance by social units with no kin and implies tolerance beyond kinship. Similarly, the
365 presence in some groups of immature individuals that are not sired by the resident silverbacks, and
366 the large mobility between social units of females with offspring may be facilitated by the absence
367 of infanticide [9,16]. Also, adults showed a high degree of tolerance during the encounters of focal
368 groups. Thus, tolerance towards members of other groups may be central to the observed dynamic
369 social structure in WLG. The distribution of pairwise genetic relatedness across sexes shows that
370 adults were mainly unrelated suggesting that, as previous studies indicated [16] and unlike most
371 primates, WLG exhibit potentially obligate natal dispersal by both sexes at maturity. At the same
372 time, males in the study area were not less related than females, as would have been expected if
373 males dispersed more frequently or over longer distances [11,45,46]. Our results also showed that
374 resident silverbacks in the study area were not more related to each other than to adult males
375 sampled alone (presumably solitary individuals), as would be expected if the latter were mainly
376 immigrants trying to establish new groups. Such males turned out to be systematically excluded as
377 offspring of resident silverbacks, but some of them had offspring across the non-breeding groups.
378 This could indicate either mating with females associated with other groups (extra-group mating) or

379 that these solitary silverbacks had led reproductive groups in the past [15]. For females,
380 relatedness analyses confirmed that closely related individuals dispersed together or tended to
381 settle in groups with same-sex relatives [43,45]. On the other hand, relatedness between females
382 and silverbacks in their own group was as expected by chance alone. All these observations
383 suggest the high mobility of both male and female breeders in and out of the study area - in
384 contrast with the sex-biased dispersal suggested by previous research [11,45,47] - that resulted in
385 very low average relatedness between adults in the studied social groups.

386 Interestingly, genealogy reconstruction showed that some pre-dispersal individuals were
387 not sired by the resident silverbacks (in groups G3, G9, and G12: figure 1a) suggesting that these
388 gorillas may have joined the groups with their dispersing mothers. On the other hand, a relevant
389 portion of the immature individuals sired by the silverbacks do not have their mothers within the
390 same group, which implies that many of these adult females might have secondarily dispersed to
391 other groups [16]. For example, two adult females in one group (G11) had their offspring in another
392 (G12). However, our data suggest that most of the secondary dispersers may have moved outside
393 the study area leaving offspring in their natal group, indicating high mobility of females, even after
394 producing offspring.

395 In WLG, immature individuals appear to be key in facilitating social interactions between
396 social units because they are less tightly associated with the rest of the group, are often found
397 sleeping apart, and are frequently moving from one group to another [48]. We also observe that
398 young individuals are less associated with the rest of the group. Previous observations have shown
399 that immature individuals are most likely age group to leave the safety ensured by their kin [12] and
400 our data revealed social play encounters between groups in which immature individuals took a
401 leading role (see table S1).

402 Play fighting, a highly plastic and versatile behaviour, is widely used in animal societies to
403 gather information on the potential role of conspecifics as competitors or social partners. In
404 particular, this competitive/cooperative interaction serves to test the willingness to invest in a

405 relationship and, simultaneously, to express their own willingness to accept vulnerability [49]. Play
406 is also sensitive to the quality of group interactions, thus reflecting the very nature of social
407 networks [50]. Thus, WLG intergroup encounters revealed strong similarities to those observed
408 among bonobos (*Pan paniscus*) as opposed to those among the more aggressive chimpanzees
409 (*Pan troglodytes*) [51]. While bonobos maintain a high motivation to play even during adulthood,
410 chimpanzees progressively engage in less play fighting sessions as their age increased [22]. This
411 study shows high motivation to play in WLG, especially in immature individuals. Gorillas
412 may use intergroup interactions to survey potential transfer and mating opportunities. Relatively
413 few studies have examined how factors such interactions within and between groups or individual
414 temperament mediate aggression and play.
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416

417
418 There is a growing body of evidence showing how association patterns in social species are
419 non-random. For instance, the interplay of shared space use and genetic relatedness shape
420 association patterns in giraffe (*Giraffa camelopardalis*) social cliques [52], while female-male
421 relationships in Guinea baboons (*Papio papio*) pairs seem to be driven by friendship beyond the
422 sexual context [53]. For this same species, high reciprocal male tolerance is not bound by genetic
423 relatedness [54], resulting into a complex multilevel society [55]. Among great apes, male tolerance
424 for non-kin is well-known in notoriously peaceful bonobos [56] and was observed even among the
425 much more aggressive chimpanzees exchanging mating tolerance for support in conflicts [57], but
426 this behaviour has not been previously described in gorillas.

427 Hence, WLGs are likely organised into a multilevel society as found in other gregarious
428 animals [2], primates included [58], where group coalescence and breakup reiterate frequently.
429 The observed hierarchical modularity may be facilitated by the large population density in the study
430 area (among the highest for this taxon) and the presence of spatially aggregated resources such
431 as fruiting trees. Even though clumped resources are generally known to promote stronger
432 territoriality and intergroup aggressiveness in some animal societies [59], they appear to be
433 associated with tolerance in gorillas. Consistent with this view, a previous study in Lossi Sanctuary

434 (figure S1) [57] found that most intergroup encounters at fruiting trees involved tolerance (64%)
435 rather than aggression (21%) or avoidance (14%).

436 Our findings showed novel intergroup interactions of high complexity underlying a
437 hierarchical and modular social organisation dominated by fluid (e.g., many weak and only a few
438 strong) interindividual associations as opposed to both ephemeral aggregations (e.g., a flock of
439 birds) and stable animal societies (e.g., a pride of lions) [2]. The modular social structure emerging
440 in this study could facilitate sharing and transmission of information (including that on kinship), or
441 increase the potential for cultural transference [60]. Nevertheless, these same intergroup
442 interactions in WLG may also play a major role in spreading infectious diseases [61-63].
443 Pathogens with high transmission potential such as *Ebolavirus* can easily travel between social
444 units, with group-living animals being more exposed than solitary ones [47,64]. Social behaviour
445 may thus have greatly contributed to the massive impact of past Ebola outbreaks [74,75] that have
446 resulted in an increase of the threat level for the species, raising major conservation concerns
447 about population declines in the future [5,6,65]. Understanding group dynamics in social species is
448 of utmost importance when coming to model the transmission of pathogens such as *Ebolavirus*
449 [67,68]. However, since the high mortality imposed by outbreaks is likely to select against this
450 social behaviour, its persistence in WLG implies that either such massive die-offs may have been
451 rare in the past, or that the associated benefits outweigh the disadvantages. In any case, the
452 peculiar social behaviour of western lowland gorillas is an outcome of its evolutionary history and
453 will definitively impact its fate.

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456 **Data accessibility.** The datasets supporting this study, including the geographic coordinates of
457 faecal samples (Dataset S1) and the consensus genotypes (Dataset S2), have been uploaded as
458 part of the supplementary material and deposited in the Dryad data repository
459 (doi:10.5061/dryad.97kg689).

460

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462 collected field data; G.F., D.V. and S.D. analysed the molecular data; G.F., P.J.L.G., R.B.M., E.R.
463 and N.M. performed the statistical analyses; G.F. wrote the first draft of the manuscript; all authors
464 contributed to discussions, review and editing.

465

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467

468

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473

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484 **Footnotes**

485 Electronic supplementary material is available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2018.2019>.

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698

699 **FIGURE LEGENDS AND TABLES**

700

701

703 **Figure 1.** Noninvasive monitoring of western lowland gorilla groups through time and space. (a)
704 Faeces of different individuals collected on the same day and place allowed identification of
705 putative groups (grey boxes). Recaptures on two consecutive days were collapsed into unique
706 sampling events for graphical simplicity. Lines mark individual resampling within the same (black)
707 or different (red) groups. For group G14, although two nests were located, only one faeces was
708 obtained and analysed. (b) Relative position of the solitary gorillas (squares) and groups (group
709 name) in the study area. Groups sampled multiple times are represented at the centroid of all the
710 locations. Red lines indicate individual transfers between social units. Patterns of co- occurrence
711 revealed 16 groups, with some of them (G3, G6, G7, G8, G16) joining because of individual
712 transfers to form a “supergroup”. (c) Group composition and family relationships of the 125
713 genetically identified individuals. Grey boxes represent groups; the white discontinuous box
714 includes all animals always sampled alone. Vertical and slanted lines indicate parent-offspring
715 relationships; horizontal lines indicate full siblings. Individuals outside the boxes represent parents
716 identified in other groups. Individuals in white insets were found in multiple groups and so appear
717 twice in the figure (labelled with a letter to facilitate identification).

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722 **Figure 2.** Internal structure and cohesiveness in group G9. The thickness of the lines connecting

723 individuals indicate the number of times they were sampled together. The colour of the line

724 indicates possible kinship relationships (father-offspring: blue; mother-offspring: pink; full-sib:

725 green, half-sib: orange; unrelated: dashed black).

726